

PREDICTION OF ELASTIC CONSTANTS, CREEP FUNCTIONS AND THERMAL PROPERTIES OF MULTIPHASE COMPOSITE MATERIALS WITH COMPOSITE OR HOLLOW SPHERICAL INCLUSIONS

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ABSTRACT

A multiphase composite filled with spherical inclusions of several types was considered. The inclusions contained two phases: kernel (the inner phase) and shell (the outer phase). By generalizing the effective medium method for the case of a four phase model "kernel - shell - matrix - equivalent homogeneous medium," the exact analytical expressions for the bulk modulus, thermal expansion coefficient, thermal conductivity, and specific heat were obtained. The solution for the shear modulus was given in the form of a non-linear equation whose coefficients are the solution of a system of 12 linear equations.

INTRODUCTION

There are different types of multiphase composite materials. In one case several types of fillers are combined in a common matrix. By appropriate selection of fillers it is possible to optimize the necessary properties of multiphase composite such as cost, weight, modulus, strength, thermal expansion, dielectric constant, and so on. One can obtain another type of multiphase composite by filling a material with encapsulated (two phase) inclusions. This procedure is especially effective to improve damping properties [1, 2]. In this paper a general case of multiphase materials filled with composite (two phase) inclusions of several types is considered.

ELASTIC CONSTANTS

Let us consider a multiphase composite filled with spherical inclusions of several types (Fig. 1a). If we leave an inclusion and a spherical layer of the matrix around it and replace the entire remaining volume of the composite by an equivalent homogeneous medium, we obtain a three phase model (Fig. 1b). We assume that elastic constants of the equivalent homogeneous medium coincide with the effective elastic constants of the multiphase composite material. We can determine the strain and stress fields in the inclusion and in the surrounding layer of matrix from the solution of the system of equations of equilibrium with specified boundary conditions. Then we consider an

Figure 1. Calculation model for a multiphase composite filled with spherical inclusions of several types. 1 - inclusion of type 1; 2 - inclusion of type 2; M - matrix; EHM - equivalent homogeneous medium.

inclusion of another type (Fig. 1c). After averaging the stresses and strains in components we obtain the elastic constants of the multiphase composite using Hooke's law:

$$\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle = C_{ijkl} \langle \varepsilon_{kl} \rangle .$$

The above described procedure is known as the effective medium method and is a variant of the self-consistent method. In a more general case, when inclusions contain two phases, "kernel" (the inner phase) and "shell" (the outer phase), we have a four phase model (Fig. 2).

BULK MODULUS

Using the effective medium method for the case of a four phase model, the following solution for the bulk modulus $K = \frac{E}{3(1-2\nu)}$ was obtained [3]:

$$\frac{1}{3K+4G} = \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{\mu_n}{\mu} \frac{1}{3K_{*n} + 4G} , \tag{1}$$

Figure 2. Four phase model: K - kernel ($0 \leq r < r_{0n}$); S - shell ($r_{0n} \leq r < r_n$); M - matrix ($r_n \leq r < r_m$); EHM - equivalent homogeneous medium ($r > r_m$).

where G is the shear modulus of the composite, N is the number of types of inclusions, μ_n is the volume fraction of inclusions of the n -th type, $\mu = \sum_{n=1}^N \mu_n$ is the total filler content, and K_{*n} is the bulk modulus of a composite filled with inclusions of one (n -th) type:

$$K_{*n} = K_m + \frac{(K_{in} - K_m)\mu}{1 + \frac{K_{in} - K_m}{K_m + \frac{4}{3}G_m}(1 - \mu)} ; \quad (2)$$

$$K_{in} = K_n + \frac{(K_{on} - K_n)f_n}{1 + \frac{K_{on} - K_n}{K_n + \frac{4}{3}G_n}(1 - f_n)} ; \quad f_n = \left(\frac{r_{on}}{r_n}\right)^3$$

Here and hereinafter, the constants with subscripts on , n and m characterize the strain and stress fields respectively in kernel, shell and matrix in the four phase model (Fig. 2). In the case of one phase inclusions ($r_{on} = 0$) Eqn (2) coincides with the expression first obtained for a three phase model in [4].

SHEAR MODULUS

The solution for the shear modulus G was obtained in the following form [3]:

$$\frac{1}{G} = \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{\mu_n}{\mu} \left\{ \left(\frac{r_{on}}{r_n}\right)^3 A_{on} \mu + \frac{7}{10v_{on}} \frac{r_{on}^5}{r_m^3} C_{on} \mu + \left[1 - \left(\frac{r_{on}}{r_n}\right)^3 \right] A_n \mu + \right. \\ \left. + \frac{7}{10v_n} \frac{r_n^5 - r_{on}^5}{r_m^3} C_n + A_{mn}(1 - \mu) + \frac{7}{10v_m} \frac{r_m^5 - r_n^5}{r_m^3} C_{mn} \right\}, \quad (3)$$

where A_{on} , C_{on} , A_n , C_n , A_{mn} , C_{mn} are the components of the solution of the following system of 12 equations:

$$a_{ij}x_j = b_i; \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, 12; \quad (4)$$

$$\vec{x} = (A_{on}, C_{on}, A_n, B_n, C_n, D_n, A_{mn}, B_{mn}, C_{mn}, D_{mn}, B, D)^T;$$

$$\vec{b} = (0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 1, \frac{1}{G}, \frac{1}{2G})^T;$$

$$\begin{array}{lll} a_{11} = G_{on}; & a_{12} = G_{on}s_3(v_{on}, r_{on}); & a_{1k} = -G_n s_{k-2}(v_n, r_{on}); \\ a_{21} = G_{on}; & a_{22} = G_{on}p_3(v_{on}, r_{on}); & a_{2k} = -G_n p_{k-2}(v_n, r_{on}); \\ a_{31} = u_1(r_{on}); & a_{32} = u_3(r_{on}); & a_{3k} = -u_{k-2}(r_{on}); \\ a_{41} = v_1(v_{on}, r_{on}); & a_{42} = v_3(v_{on}, r_{on}); & a_{4k} = -v_{k-2}(v_{on}, r_{on}); \\ a_{5k} = G_n s_{k-2}(v_n, r_n); & a_{5l} = -G_m s_{l-6}(v_m, r_n); & a_{6k} = G_n p_{k-2}(v_n, r_n); \\ a_{6l} = -G_m p_{l-6}(v_m, r_n); & a_{7k} = u_{k-2}(r_n); & a_{7l} = -u_{l-6}(r_n); \\ a_{8k} = v_{k-2}(v_n, r_n); & a_{8l} = -v_{l-6}(v_m, r_n); & a_{9l} = s_{l-6}(v_m, r_m); \\ a_{9,11} = 4G; & a_{9,12} = 2G \frac{5-v}{5-4v}; & a_{10,l} = p_{l-6}(v_m, r_m); \\ a_{10,11} = -\frac{8}{3}G; & a_{10,12} = -2G \frac{1+v}{5-4v}; & a_{11,l} = u_{l-6}(r_m); \\ a_{11,11} = -1; & a_{11,12} = -1; & a_{12,l} = v_{l-6}(r_m); \end{array}$$

$$a_{12,11} = \frac{1}{3}; \quad a_{12,11} = -\frac{1-2\nu}{5-4\nu}; \quad k = 3, 4, 5, 6; \quad l = 7, 8, 9, 10;$$

and the remaining coefficients a_{ij} are equal to zero;

$$\bar{s}(v, r) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ -4r^{-5} \\ -\frac{1}{2}r^2 \\ -2\frac{5-\nu}{5-4\nu}r^{-3} \end{pmatrix}; \quad \bar{p}(v, r) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \frac{8}{3}r^{-5} \\ \frac{7+2\nu}{6\nu}r^2 \\ 2\frac{1+\nu}{5-4\nu}r^{-3} \end{pmatrix};$$

$$\bar{u}(r) = \begin{pmatrix} r \\ r^{-4} \\ r^3 \\ r^{-2} \end{pmatrix}; \quad \bar{v}(v, r) = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2}r \\ -\frac{1}{3}r^{-4} \\ \frac{7-4\nu}{12\nu}r^3 \\ \frac{1-2\nu}{5-4\nu}r^{-2} \end{pmatrix}.$$

In the case of one phase inclusions of the same type ($r_{0n} = 0$ and $N = 1$) Eqn (4) reduces to a system of 8 equations. It is possible to show that in this case Eqn (3) gives the same solution as the expression first obtained for a three phase model in [5].

CREEP FUNCTIONS

Let the components of the multiphase composite material be of a linear viscoelastic character. In this case the deformation of the components can be described with linear integral equations of a hereditary type:

$$\varepsilon_{ij}^n(t) = \int_0^t I_{ijkl}^n(t-t') \frac{d\sigma_{kl}^n(t')}{dt'} dt', \quad (5)$$

where $n = 0$ corresponds to the matrix and $n = 1, 2, \dots, 2N$ corresponds to the other phases. If we apply the Laplace transform to Eqn (5), we obtain the following equations

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_{ij}^n(s) = s\bar{I}_{ijkl}^n(s)\bar{\sigma}_{kl}^n(s),$$

which are analogous to the equations of an elastic problem. Here the upper line is used to designate Laplace representations and s is a transform parameter. By using the solution of the problem of determining of elastic moduli of the multiphase composite, where compliances I_{ijkl}^n of the components are replaced by $s\bar{I}_{ijkl}^n(s)$, and also by replacing the stresses σ_{ij} applied to the composite at $r \rightarrow \infty$ by $\frac{\bar{\sigma}_{ij}(s)}{s}$, we shall obtain the Laplace representations for viscoelastic strains of multiphase composite. Using the inversion of the Laplace transform, it is then possible to determine the desired creep functions $I_{ijkl}(t)$ of the composite.

THERMAL EXPANSION COEFFICIENT

For determining the effective coefficient of thermal expansion α , an equilibrium state of an unloaded multiphase composite after its heating from temperature T_0 to $T_0 + \Delta T$ was considered. The following expression was obtained [3]:

$$\frac{K\alpha}{3K+4G} = \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{\mu_n}{\mu} \frac{K_{*n}\alpha_{*n}}{3K_{*n}+4G}, \quad (6)$$

where α_{*n} is the effective coefficient of thermal expansion of a composite filled with inclusions of one (n -th) type:

$$\alpha_{*n} = \alpha_m + \frac{\alpha_{1n} - \alpha_m}{\frac{1}{K_{1n}} - \frac{1}{K_m}} \left(\frac{1}{K_{*n}} - \frac{1}{K_m} \right); \quad (7)$$

$$\alpha_{1n} = \alpha_n + \frac{\alpha_{0n} - \alpha_n}{\frac{1}{K_{0n}} - \frac{1}{K_n}} \left(\frac{1}{K_{1n}} - \frac{1}{K_n} \right).$$

In the case of one phase inclusions Eqn (7) coincides with the expression first obtained for a three phase model in [6] and, independently, in [7, 8].

SPECIFIC HEAT

For determining the specific heat of a multiphase composite, the change in the internal energy of a unit volume of the material resulting from slow heating from temperature T_0 to $T_0 + dT$ was examined. The temperature field in composite at each moment of time was assumed to be uniform. The first law of thermodynamics was used. As a result the following expression for the specific heat at constant stress c_σ was obtained [3], which takes into account the amount of energy spent on the work against the elastic forces arising in components during their thermal expansion:

$$\rho c_\sigma = \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{\mu_n}{\mu} \rho_{*n} c_{\sigma}^{*n} + 36T_0 \left[\frac{K\alpha^2}{3K+4G} - \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{\mu_n}{\mu} \frac{K_{*n}(\alpha_{*n})^2}{3K_{*n}+4G} \right], \quad (8)$$

where $\rho = \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{\mu_n}{\mu} \rho_{*n}$ is the density of multiphase composite, and c_{σ}^{*n} is the specific heat of a composite filled with inclusions of one (n -th) type:

$$\rho_{*n} c_{\sigma}^{*n} = \mu \rho_n c_{\sigma}^{1n} + (1-\mu) \rho_m c_{\sigma}^m - 9T_0 \frac{\mu(1-\mu)(\alpha_{1n}-\alpha_m)^2}{\frac{1-\mu}{K_{1n}} + \frac{\mu}{K_m} + \frac{3}{4G_m}}; \quad \rho_{*n} = \mu \rho_{1n} + (1-\mu) \rho_m; \quad (9)$$

$$\rho_n c_{\sigma}^{1n} = f_n \rho_{0n} c_{\sigma}^{0n} + (1-f_n) \rho_n c_{\sigma}^n - 9T_0 \frac{f_n(1-f_n)(\alpha_{0n}-\alpha_n)^2}{\frac{1-f_n}{K_{0n}} + \frac{f_n}{K_n} + \frac{3}{4G_n}}; \quad \rho_{1n} = f_n \rho_{0n} + (1-f_n) \rho_n.$$

In the case of one phase inclusions Eqn (9) coincides with the expression first obtained in [8].

THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY

For determining the temperature and heat flux fields in components in the case of a stationary temperature field, a heat conduction equation was solved. As in the previous problem, a four phase model was used. After averaging the temperature gradients and heat fluxes in components the effective thermal conductivity λ of the multiphase composite was obtained in the form [3]:

$$\frac{1}{3\lambda} = \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{\mu_n}{\mu} \frac{1}{2\lambda + \lambda_{*n}}, \quad (10)$$

where λ_{*n} is the effective thermal conductivity of a composite filled with inclusions of one (n -th) type:

$$\lambda_{*n} = \lambda_m \left[1 + \frac{3(\lambda_{in} - \lambda_m)\mu}{3\lambda_m + (\lambda_{in} - \lambda_m)(1 - \mu)} \right]; \quad (11)$$

$$\lambda_{in} = \lambda_n \left[1 + \frac{3(\lambda_{on} - \lambda_n)f_n}{3\lambda_n + (\lambda_{on} - \lambda_n)(1 - f_n)} \right].$$

In the case of one phase inclusions Eqn (11) coincides with the expression first obtained for a three phase model in [9].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It was shown [10-12] that the effective medium method can be successfully used to predict the experimental data for composite materials filled with solid glass microspheres if $\mu \leq 0.35-0.40$ (the ratio of the modulus of glass inclusions E_g to the modulus of polyester matrix E_m was within the range 23 - 42). In the case of pores ($E_p = 0$) the predicted results are exact enough till $\mu = 0.6$.

Computed and experimental [13] values of the elastic modulus of a composite filled with hollow glass spheres are compared in Fig. 3. The elastic constants of the components and the average value of thickness-to-diameter ratio ψ , which are required to perform the calculations, were taken

Figure 3. Elastic modulus of hollow glass sphere composite. Dots represent experimental data [13]. Curves are described in the text; $\psi = 0.02$.

from [13]. The curve 1 was computed using Kerner's solutions [4] for a three phase model of a composite filled with spherical inclusions. It is necessary to mention that Kerner [4] obtained the exact solution for bulk modulus K and an approximate solution for G (which coincides with Hashin and Shtrikman's highest lower bound). The so-called two step approach was used, with the first step to calculate the effective moduli of a hollow sphere and the second step to calculate the effective moduli of the composite. The curve 2 was computed using Eqs (2) and (3). One can see that curve 2 fits the experimental data better than Kerner's solution. It was found in [14] that the discrepancy between the two methods in the case of the elastic modulus E increases as the ratio of the glass shell modulus E_g to the matrix modulus E_m increases and can reach 13% when $E_g / E_m = 15$ or up to 17% if $E_g / E_m = 100$.

One can conclude from Fig. 3 that the effective medium method exhibits sufficient accuracy when $\mu \leq 0.5$. In [13] the same range for μ was found in the case of the thermal expansion coefficient and the thermal conductivity (Eqs (7) and (11)).

Calculated results of the creep function $I_{1111}(t) = \frac{\epsilon_{11}(t)}{\sigma_{11}}$ of the same hollow glass sphere composite with filler volume content $\mu = 0.5$ are shown in Fig. 4. The hollow glass spheres were assumed to be elastic. The master curve [15] of tensile creep of the epoxy EDT-10 matrix was used. Poisson's ratio of the matrix was assumed to be 0.42 when $t = 0$. The second independent creep function of the matrix was defined on the assumption that the bulk modulus K_m of the matrix does not change with the passage of time. An algorithm of the quadrature interpolation formulae [16] was used for the numerical inversion of the Laplace transform. Curve 1 was computed using Kerner's solutions. Curve 2 was calculated using Eqs (2) and (3). The discrepancy between the two methods was found to be up to 63% at a hollow sphere volume content $\mu = 0.5$ (or up to 34% at $\mu = 0.4$ [14]).

Figure 4. Computed values of master creep function $I_{1111}(t)$ of composite containing hollow spherical fillers for $\mu = 0.5$, $\bar{\psi} = 0.02$. Curves are described in the text.

It is obvious that hollow spheres always have some scattering in values of the thickness-to-diameter ratio ψ . The solutions (1), (3), (6), (8), (10) can be easily modified for the case of a continuous distribution of the parameter ψ by replacing the sums of type $\sum_{n=1}^N \frac{\mu_n}{\mu} X_n$ with the integrals $\frac{1}{F} \int_0^1 X(\psi) f(\psi) d\psi$, where $f(\psi)$ is the distribution function and $F = \int_0^1 f(\psi) d\psi$. The curves 3 and 4 in Fig. 3 and curve 3 in Fig. 4 were calculated using Weibull's distribution function

$$f(\psi) = \alpha\beta\psi^{\beta-1} \exp(-\alpha\psi^\beta).$$

with $\beta = 2$ (curve 4 in Fig. 3 and curve 3 in Fig. 4) and $\beta = 5$ (curve 3 on Fig. 3).

One can see that the discrepancy between computed values of modulus E increases as β decreases, i.e. as the distribution function $f(\psi)$ becomes wider and more asymmetrical (see curves 2-4 in Fig. 3). At $\mu = 0.5$ the discrepancy is equal 1% when $\beta = 5$ and is equal 5% when $\beta = 2$. The maximum relative discrepancy between the curves 2 and 3 in Fig. 4 is equal 9%.

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